

TRUST AWARE ROUTING FOR WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT:

A Wireless sensor network (WSN) is usually composed of a large number of spatially distributed autonomous sensor nodes(SNs) to cooperatively monitor physical or environmental conditions, such as temperature, sound, vibration, pressure, motion or pollutants. A WSN deployed in the WSN has the capability to read the sensed information and transmit or forward information to base stations or a sink node through multi-hop routing. Due to dynamic and unpredictable changing behaviour of nodes, there liable data delivery is a challenging task. For WSNs, the traditional cryptographic and authentication-based solutions cannot be adopted due to their associated cost and in capability to count er nodes misbehaviour attacks. Here we develop a new trust ensuring mechanism with multi contextual aspects including the interactions between the WSN nodes and their energy levels. Furthermore, a minimum hop count mechanism is also proposed to select a path with less processing delay. Since the energy is also an important factor, this approach focused to reduce the overall energy consumption also. The performance is measured through the performance metrics namely, packet deliver ratio, Malicious Detection Rate (MDR), and False Positive Rate (FPR)

KEYWORDS: Wireless sensor networks, trust management, Routing, Average packet delivery ratio, False positive rate, malicious detection rate.

INTRODUCTION:

Wireless Sensor Networks has an important role in the area of wireless technology. A wireless network which consists of tiny devices which able to monitor physical or environmental conditions such as temperature, pressure, motion or pollutants etc. at different areas. network.

Wireless sensor networks are most important technologies in present technology of the world. Development in wireless communications and electronics has enabled the development of low-cost, low-power, multifunctional miniature devices for use in remote sensing applications. The combination of these factors has improved the viability of utilizing a sensor network consisting of a large number of intelligent sensors, enabling the collection, processing analysis and dissemination of valuable information gathered in a variety of environments. A sensor network is composed of a large number of sensor nodes which consist of sensing, data processing and communication capabilities. Sensor network protocols and

algorithms must possess self-organizing capabilities.

Another feature of sensor networks is the cooperative effort of sensor nodes. Sensor nodes are suitable with an onboard processor. Instead of sending the raw data to the nodes responsible for the fusion, they use their processing abilities to locally carry out simple computations and transmit only the required and partially processed data.

MULTICONTEXT TRUST AWARE ROUTING:

Trust Estimation

The trust estimation component evaluates the trustworthiness of neighbor nodes by overhearing their transmission in promiscuous mode and dynamically identifies misbehaving nodes. Each sensor node maintains a buffer to store information such as Packet ID, Next-hop ID, Sender and receiver IDs. Assume node i , node j and node k participate in packet forwarding between a pair of source and destination nodes and are neighbors, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Node Monitoring

The trust model (at node i and node k) categorize each of the monitor sensor nodes (node j) in either of category, based on monitored information: *trusted node*, *malicious node* and *faulty node*. Node j is considered as trusted node if node i and node k finds the match in corresponding entries. The total trust $T_{i,j}(t)$ can be defined as weighted aggregated sum of three components:

$$T_{i,j}(t) = w_1 DT_{i,j}(t) + w_2 \frac{IT_{i,j}(t)}{N_j} \quad (2.1)$$

$DT_{i,j}(t)$ denotes the degree of direct trust node i has for node j at time t , based on the node i 's observation of packet forwarding behavior for node j . $IT_{i,j}(t)$ represents the average degree of indirect trust node i has gained using recommendations from its neighbors (k) for node j at time t . N_j represents a set consisting of neighbors for node j . The weight factors w_1 and w_2 are assigned to $DT_{i,j}(t)$ and $IT_{i,j}(t)$ respectively, such that $w_1 + w_2 = 1$, whereas $0 \leq w_1 \leq 1$ and $0 \leq w_2 \leq 1$. An indirect trust is determined from the observations gained through interactions with neighbors who notifies about their own direct observation for particular node. The indirect trust $IT_{i,j}(t)$ is determined using Eq. (3.3).

$$\sum_{k \in N_j, k \neq i} IT_{i,j}^k(t) = \sum_{k \in N_j, k \neq i} DT_{i,k}(t) \times DT_{k,j}(t) \quad (2.2)$$

$DT_{k,j}(t)$ represents the degree of direct trust evaluated by node k for node j (common neighbour of node i and node k). $DT_{i,k}(t)$ denotes the direct trust between nodes i and k . Incorporating $DT_{i,k}(t)$ ensures that the node providing recommendations is trusted entity.

. For example, a malicious node may tamper with the data, may misroute packet to other network part or may forward the packet to other malicious node. Such forwarding is not considered as correct or successful forwarding. The direct trust is evaluated as in Eq. 2.3.

$$DT_{i,j}(t) = \frac{CF_{i,j}(t)}{TR_{i,j}(t)} \quad (2.3)$$

$CF_{i,j}(t)$ denotes total number of correctly forwarded packets by node i at time j , whereas $TR_{i,j}(t)$ represents total number of received packets by node i from node j at time t . For each node, initial trust degree is set to 0.5 (indecisive node) that opt a neutral view on unknown nodes.

1 Energy Trust

It is a necessary to consider the energy is also a significant factor in the trust evaluation. Since the energy is a necessary thing for both reception and transmission of data from every sensor node, this approach considers both contexts including the reception and transmission states for energy trust evaluation. The mathematical representations for the energy cost for reception and transmission are represented as

$$RC(k, d) = E_{elec} \times k$$

$$TC(k, d) = E_{elec} \times k + E_{amp} \times k \times d^2$$

Where RC is receiving Cost, TC is transmitting cost, k is the number of message bits, d is the distance between node i and node j . E_{elec} represents the unit energy consumption for transmitting the message at node j , and E_{amp} represent the unit energy consumption for achieving particular SNR during transmission. The total energy consumption cost at node j can be estimated as the sum of receiving energy and transmitting energy and it is obtained as;

$$TEC = 2 \times E_{elec} \times k + E_{amp} \times k \times d^2$$

If the initial energy of a node is EB , the remaining energy ES of node j is measured as

$$ES = EB - TEC$$

Based on the above equation, a capability of a node will be decided whether it is able to cooperate with other nodes or not in the data transmission. The remaining energy ES of a node is compared with a predefined threshold, E_{th} and if it is greater than the threshold E_{th} , then that particular node is said to be capable

otherwise it cannot participate in the data transmission. Though the node is observed as high trustworthy, if its ES is less than the threshold, it cannot participate in the data transmission. Based on these, the trust degree of node j with respect to the energy is defined as

$$ET_y = \begin{cases} 1, & ES \geq E_{th} \\ 0, & ES < E_{th} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

In this manner, based on the energy levels of node, it can be selected as next hop node for forwarding data if it has sufficient energy trust degree. Similar to the Communication trust evaluation, the energy trust also measured both in direct fashion and recommended fashion. The total energy trust between node i and node j can be measured as

$$ET_{i,j} = w_1 \times DET_{i,j} + w_2 \times \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{RET_{k,j}^i}{N_k} \quad (3.6)$$

$DET_{i,j}$ denotes the degree of direct energy trust between node i and node j , based on the node i 's observation for node j . $RET_{k,j}^i$ is the indirect/recommended energy trust gained by the node i through the neighboring node k of node j . Similar to the illustration given in the communication trust evaluation, the recommended trust is an average trust of k neighboring node of node i . The recommended energy trust $RET_{k,j}(t)$ is determined using Eq. 3.7.

$$\sum_{k \in N_k, k \neq j} RET_{k,j}^i = \sum_{k \in N_k, k \neq j} DET_{i,k} \times DET_{k,j} \quad (3.7)$$

Where $DET_{i,k}$ represents the direct energy trust between the node i and neighbouring node k of node j and $DET_{k,j}$ represents the direct trust between the node j and neighbouring node k .

Hop count:

The **hop count** refers to the number of intermediate devices through which data must pass between source and destination. Hop count should be less.

3.2. Trust and Energy aware Routing

This multi-facet strategy also reduces extra overhead required in exchanging additional control packets for trust and energy. The characteristics that leads to the selection of AODV protocol are: on-demand routing, less control overheads, maintain latest routing information, both unicast and broadcast capability, low connection setup time, reduced storage cost and scalability features. Proposed introduces a Composite Routing Function (CRF) metric that incorporates nodes' trust, remaining energy and hop counts. The trust, remaining energy and hop count are summed up in weighted manner to compute the cost for CRF as shown in Eq. (3.8).

$$CRF = \alpha * trust + \beta * Energy + \gamma * Hop\ count \quad (3.8)$$

The weights α, β and γ represent the significance of trust, energy and hop count respectively, where $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$. By default, all weights have been given uniform proportion in order to have equal impact in route selection. These weights may be varied according to applications' requirement. The node that optimizes this composite routing function is selected in routing path as it represents a suitable candidate satisfying integrated set of requirements. High throughput is achieved when trusted nodes are selected for packet forwarding. Energy awareness is incorporated in the routing process such that only those trusted nodes are selected to route the packets whose residual energy level is above the specified threshold.

3.1 Block diagram of proposed system

Results:

To realise the proposed trust aware routing mechanism, initially a random network is

created with the give number of nodes.in the simulation environment the inputs to be entered by the user like:

1.Enter the number of nodes:35

Fig1: Network formation

Secondly, we have to enter the inputs like:

Enter the Source Node: 2

Enter the Destination Node: 16

Number of possible paths in the network between source and destination node= 6

Selected Path:

Based on communication trust and hop count the selected path is path-1. This path-1 consists of different nodes node -2, node -4, node -32, node -22, node -16.

The intermediate node count is = 3

We prefer this path compared to other possible paths as it has fewer intermediate nodes. And the communication trust is best.

Hop count:

The **hop count** refers to the number of intermediate devices through which data must

pass between source and destination. Hop count should be less.

Malicious node:

It is a node seeking to Deny Service to other nodes in the network and it also modifies the data before, during or after the transmission.

Here two malicious nodes are detected.

Malicious Nodes Detected:

24 7 33 33 33

CRM_MCTAR =5.0400

Composite Routing Metric (CRM): It is defined as the summation of Communication trust, hop count and Energy trust with appropriate weighing factors.

$$CRM = \alpha * CT + \beta * HC + \gamma * ET \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma = \text{arbitrary constants}$$

CT = Communication Trust; HC = Hop count; ET = Energy trust

Parameters to calculate: APDR, MDR, FPR

Average Packet Deliver Ratio:

- It is defined as the ratio of total packets delivered to the destination to the total packets transmitted.
- The higher value of APDR indicates the good performance and lower value indicates the bad performance.

- Average packet deliver ratio should be high for efficient transmission. It is high for proposed method when compared with existing method.

MDR- Malicious Detection Rate

It is defined as ratio of total malicious nodes detected to the total malicious nodes present.

- Higher MDR indicates the good performance and lower MDR indicates bad performance.

MDR = True Positive / True Positive + False Negative

True Positive = Number of faulty nodes detected correctly.

False Negative = Number of faulty nodes detected as non-faulty.

- Here the performance is evaluated by counting the total number of nodes detected as malicious when they are really malicious.

FPR- False Positive Ratio / FAR (False alarm rate):

- It is the ratio of the non-faulty nodes detected as faulty to the total number of fault free nodes.

- Higher FPR indicates the bad performance and the lower FPR indicates good performance.

FPR= False Negative / True Positive + False Negative

True Positive = Number of faulty nodes detected correctly

False Negative = Number of faulty nodes detected as non-faulty

Conclusion:

In this paper , we propose a new trust and energy aware routing protocol (TERP) for enhancing the security of WSN in presence of several malicious and faulty nodes. TERP focuses on two critical factors trustworthiness and energy efficiency, which are most essential for the survival of WSN in hostile conditions and strong attacks. TERP guides the sensor nodes to forwards packets through shortest paths that consist of trusted and energy-efficient nodes that lead to balancing the energy consumption among trusted nodes. The weights introduced in trust estimation and as well as in composite routing metric allows flexible customization and configuration, fine tuning of algorithm and tradeoff between various parameters. The combined concept of trust and energy management enables TERP to keep record of trustworthiness and energy levels of participating nodes. This multi-facet

strategy helps to select a reliable and energy efficient route which is vital for the network lifetime of WSN. The simulation results reveal improved performance of TERP as compared to existing schemes. The performance evaluation carried out in various aspects such as throughput analysis, delay analysis, load analysis and lifetime analysis for the proposed TERP scheme is observed to be more efficient compared with earlier TSRF and LTB-AODV. The through for increasing number of malicious nodes is observed to be a decremented function but compared to the TSRF and LTB-AODV, it is higher. Similarly the delay of TERP is less, lesser normalized routing load and finally an enhanced lifetime compared to earlier approaches.

5.2 Future Scope

In future, we aim to enhance the trust model's design so that it may counter other node misbehavior attacks such as Sybil, wormhole and selfishness. Our TERP scheme offers a lightweight solution for resource constrained sensor nodes, yet its efficacy on real hardware platform needs to be confirmed. We also aim to develop a small test-bed for real implementation of the proposed TERP scheme.

References

- [1] W. Su Y. Sankarasubramaniam E. CayirciAkyildiz, I.F. A survey on sensor-networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, pages 102-114, 2002.
- [2] Kumar.S.P. Chee-Yee Chong. Sensor networks: Evolution, opportunities, and challenges. *Proc IEEE*, August 2003.
- [3] Ismail H. KasimogluIan .F. Akyildiz. Wireless sensor and actor: research challenges. (*Elsevier*) *Journal*, 2(38):351-367, 2004.
- [4] Sungha Pete Kim Bo-Cheng Charles Lai, David D. Hwang. Reducing radio energy consumption of key management protocols for wireless sensor networks. *ACM 1-58113-929-2/04/0008*, pages 9-11, August 2004.
- [5] Sarika Agarwal Leszek LilienMaleq Khan, Bharat Bhargava and Pankaj. Self-configuring node clusters, data aggregation, and security in micro sensor networks. *Department of Management Information Systems Krannert Graduate School of Management Purdue University, West Lafayette, (IN 47907)*, 2007. pankaj@mgmt.purdue.edu.
- [6] Sundeep Karthikeyan Vaidynathan, Sayantan sur and Sinha. Data aggregation techniques in sensor networks. *Technical Report, OSU-CISRC-11/04-TR60*, 2004.
- [7] D. Agrawal N. Shrivastava, C. Buragohain and S. Suri. Medians and beyond: new aggregation techniques for sensor networks. *Proceedings of the 2nd international conference on Embedded networked sensor systems*, pages 239{249, 2004. ACM Press.
- [8] Xiuli Ren and Haibin Yu1. Security mechanisms for wireless sensor networks. *IJCSNS International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, VOL.6 (No.3):100{107, March 2006.
- [9] S. Setia S. Zhu and S. Jajodia. Leap: efficient security mechanisms for large scale distributed sensor networks. *Proceedings of the 10th ACM conference on Computer and communications security*, pages 62{72, 2003. ACM Press.
- [10] J. Stankovic A. Perrig and D. Wagner. Security in wireless sensor networks.
- [11] P.NairH.Cam, S.Ozdemir and D. Muthuavinashiappan. Espda: Energy efficient and secure pattern based data aggregation for wireless sensor networks. *Computer Communications IEEE Sensors*, 29:446-455, 2006.
- [12] Jonathan Jen-Rong Chen Prasan Kumar Sahoo and Ping-Tai Sun. efficient security mechanisms for the distributed wireless sensor networks. *Proceedings of the IEEE Third International Conference on Information Technology and Applications (ICITA'05)*, pages 0{7695{2316{1, 2005.
- [13] Vijay Garg b M.S. Meitei c S. Raman c A. Kumar c N. Tewari R.K. Ghosh a, Ad hoc networks. pages 168-185, 2006.
- [14] Wei Ding and et.al. Energy equivalence routing in wireless sensor networks.

- [15] J. Duan, D. Yang, H. Zhu, S. Zhang, and J. Zhao, "TSRF: A Trust-Aware Secure Routing Framework in Wireless Sensor Networks," *Int. J. Distrib. Sens. Networks*, vol. 2014, no. Article ID 209436, pp. 1–14, 2014.
- [16] J. Cordasco and S. Wetzel, "Cryptographic Versus Trustbased Methods for MANET Routing Security," *Electron. Notes Theor. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 197, no. 2, pp. 131–140, Feb. 2008.
- [17] Y. Yu, K. Li, W. Zhou, and P. Li, "Trust mechanisms in wireless sensor networks: Attack analysis and countermeasures," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 867–880, May 2012.
- [18] M. C. Fernandez-Gago, R. Roman, and J. Lopez, "A Survey on the Applicability of Trust Management Systems for Wireless Sensor Networks," in *Third IEEE International Workshop on Security, Privacy and Trust in Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing, 2007. SECPerU, 2007*, no. SecPerU, pp. 25–30.
- [19] T. Zahariadis, P. Trakadas, H. C. Leligou, S. Maniatis, and P. Karkazis, "A Novel Trust-Aware Geographical Routing Scheme for Wireless Sensor Networks," *Wirel. Pers. Commun.*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 805–826, Apr. 2012.
- [20] L. Gheorghe, R. Rughiniş, and N. Țăpuş, "Trust and Energy-aware Routing Protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks," in *The Eighth International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Communications (ICWMC)*, 2012, pp. 388–394.
- [21] M. I. Channa and K. M. Ahmed, "A Reliable Routing Scheme for Post-Disaster Ad Hoc Communication Networks," *J. Commun.*, vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 549–557, Oct. 2011.
- [22] N. Marchang and R. Datta, "Light-weight trust-based routing protocol for mobile ad hoc networks," *IET Inf. Secur.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 77–83, 2012.
- [23] T. Eissa, S. Abdul Razak, R. H. Khokhar, and N. Samian, "Trust-Based Routing Mechanism in MANET: Design and Implementation," *Mob. Networks Appl.*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 666–677, Jun. 2013.
- [24] D. Wei, Y. Jin, S. Vural, K. Moessner, and R. Tafazolli, "An Energy-Efficient Clustering Solution for Wireless Sensor Networks," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 10, no. 11, pp. 3973–3983, 2011.
- [25] N. A. Pantazis, S. A. Nikolidakis, and D. D. Vergados, "Energy-Efficient Routing Protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks : A Survey," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 551–591, 2013.
- [26] J. Duan, D. Gao, C. H. Foh, and H. Zhang, "TC-BAC: A trust and centrality degree based access control model in wireless sensor networks," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 2675–2692, Nov. 2013.
- [27] Y. Sun, H. Luo, and S. K. Das, "A Trust-Based Framework for Fault-Tolerant Data Aggregation in Wireless Multimedia Sensor Networks," *IEEE Trans. Dependable Secur. Comput.*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 785–797, 2012.
- [28] S. Chen, Y. Zhang, Q. Liu, and J. Feng, "Dealing with dishonest recommendation: The trials in reputation management court," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 1603–1618, Nov. 2012.
- [29] J. Cho, A. Swami, and I. Chen, "A Survey on Trust Management for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 562–583, 2011.
- [30] H. Deng, G. Jin, K. Sun, R. Xu, M. Lyell, and J. A. Luke, "Trust-Aware In-Network Aggregation for Wireless Sensor Networks," in *Proceedings of IEEE Global Telecommunications conference (GLOBECOM)*, 2009, no. 978, pp. 1–8.